

PHYSICAL ACTIVITIES OF GRAMMAR AND VOCATIONAL SCHOOL STUDENTS AFTER RETURNING TO SCHOOL FOLLOWING THE FOURTH WAVE OF COVID-19 IN EASTERN SLOVAKIA

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Abstract

The progress of society is an inevitable process that apart from its multiple benefits has also brought about disadvantages, for example, the spread of physical inactivity. For the past three years the humankind has suffered from the COVID-19 pandemic, which has isolated many people and necessitated working and studying from home thus bringing more sedentary time into human lives. The aim of this study was to assess and compare physical activity levels of grammar and vocational school students after they returned to school following the fourth wave of COVID-19 pandemic in eastern Slovakia. The study data was obtained from respondents' answers to the International Physical Activity Questionnaire - Short Form (IPAQ-SF) consisting of seven questions regarding physical activity. The survey group comprised 300 grammar school students and 199 vocational school students aged 17.31 \pm 1.44 years. After having reviewed the answers, the students were divided into three physical activity level groups: high, moderate, and low. Next, the students' results were compared based on the type of school they attended, with the use of unpaired t-test and chi-squared test (X^2) ($p < 0.01$ or $p < 0.05$). The grammar school students were more active at the moderate and low levels, while the vocational school students were more active at the high level. The latter engaged in vigorous physical activity for 12.5 minutes per week longer than the grammar school students. The observed differences were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

Key words: physical activities, COVID-19, students, IPAQ

Introduction

Since children usually spend around 6 hours a day sitting at school it is essential for them to move and engage in physical activity. Children also spend their time sitting in many other places outside school. The amount of screen time spent during COVID-19 pandemic increased significantly and exceeded 8 hours a day [1]. As reported by Strasburger et al. [2] the average time of multimedia use by 8-18-year-olds in the USA was around 75 hours a week. These figures are comparable with those in Europe [3]. Tremblay et al. [4] recommended reducing screen time to no more than 2 hours per day. As shown by Gibbs et al. [5] excessive sedentary time has multiple negative health effects among children and adolescents

worldwide. Physical inactivity causes various health problems such as diabetes, obesity, cancer, joint diseases, and depression [5]. Myers et al. [6] demonstrated more than a 50% decrease in cardiovascular diseases in a group of fit people, who regularly engaged in physical activities in comparison to those who did not. 81% of adolescents of different genders worldwide are considered to be insufficiently physically active [7]. The World Health Organization recommendations for physical activity of moderate to vigorous intensity for 5-17-year-olds is 60 minutes per day with addition of vigorous-intensity aerobic activities at least 3 days a week [8]. As for adults the World Health Organization recommends

engagement in moderate-intensity aerobic physical activity for 150-300 minutes, or for at least 75-150 minutes of vigorous-intensity aerobic physical activity a week [8]. Reduction of screen time and avoidance of sedentary time are recommended for both adolescents and adults [9].

However, despite the well-known benefits and widely available information, it is estimated that more than one-third of the world's population fails to meet the minimum recommendations for physical activity [10]. People who are not physically active and thus suffer from preventable diseases are responsible for 0.3% – 4.6% of national healthcare expenditures worldwide [6, 11, 12]. Lee et al. [13] estimated that a shift from physical inactivity to physical activity could prevent 5.3 million deaths per year and increase life expectancy by 0.68 a year. Min [14] concluded that the average medical costs for a physically active person in Korea were 11.7% lower than for a physically non-active one.

Methods

The questionnaire survey involved 499 17-18-year-old 3rd- or 4th-grade Slovakian grammar school students (n = 300) and vocational school students (n = 199) after their return to school following the fourth wave of COVID-19 pandemic. Table 1 presents more detailed characteristics of the respondents. The main reason for dividing the surveyed students into two groups based on school type was the different education profile offered in secondary grammar and vocational schools in Slovakia. Education in grammar schools focuses on providing general knowledge from all subjects and lasts 4, 5 or 8 years, whereas secondary vocational schools focus specifically on professional training in specific areas and their curriculum may comprise up to 50% of practical classes. The educational process in grammar schools is aimed at preparing students for higher education.

Table 1. Characteristics of the survey group of grammar and vocation school students.

	Grammar school students	Vocational school students	Total
Age	17.18	17.44	17.31
BMI	21.43	22.74	22.1

The respondents' physical activity (PA) was measured with the International Physical Activity Questionnaire – Short Form (IPAQ-SF). The questionnaire included 7 questions regarding frequency (days per week) and duration (minutes) of walking, moderate physical activity, and vigorous physical activity. Vigorous physical activity was defined as intense exercise resulting in an elevated heart rate and rapid breathing (aerobic activities, cycling, running, and body conditioning training). Moderate physical activity was defined as exercise resulting in a slightly elevated heart rate and accelerated breathing (fast walking, light weightlifting). Data from the questionnaires were converted to Metabolic Equivalent of Task units per week (MET-minutes/week) calculated by multiplying the number of exercising minutes per day by the

number of exercises per week by the MET coefficient of physical activity intensity (vigorous PA = 8 MET, moderate PA = 4 MET, walking PA = 3.3 MET). The MET coefficient of exercise intensity represents a person's oxygen consumption during physical activity corresponding to oxygen consumption at rest. The respondents were then divided into three different groups based on the following criteria:

1. High physical activity – three or more days of vigorous physical exercise, including at least 1,500 MET-minutes/week, or seven or more days of any combination of vigorous exercise, moderate exercise, and walking that exceeded 3,000 MET-minutes/week (<https://sites.google.com/site/theipaq/scoring-protocol>);

2. Moderate physical activity – three or more days of vigorous physical exercise (at least 20 minutes per day), or five or more days of moderate exercise or walking (at least 30 minutes per day), or five or more days of a combination of vigorous exercise, moderate exercise, and walking that exceeded 600 MET-minutes/week (<https://sites.google.com/site/theipaq/scoring-protocol>);
3. Low physical activity – little physical activity resulting in a failure to comply with the conditions of moderate or high physical activity classifications (less than 600 MET-minutes/week) (<https://sites.google.com/site/theipaq/scoring-protocol>).

The statistical data were entered into a Microsoft Excel sheet. The basic statistics included arithmetic means and medians. The results were analyzed from the perspective of different genders with the use of chi-square test (X^2) and an unpaired t-test at the level of statistical significance of $p < 0.05$ and $p < 0.01$.

Results

First, the students' physical activity levels were compared based on school type. Figure 1 shows that high physical activity dominated in students from both types of schools (69.67% of grammar schools students, and 72.86% of vocational schools students). The mean differences between the school types regarding low physical activity were small and amounted only to 0.78% in favour of the grammar schools. Students whose weekly MET-minutes did not exceed 600 were classified into the moderate physical activity group (19% from grammar schools, 16.58% from vocational schools). The comparison of findings of the present study with those of a study of Polish school students by Bergier et al. [15] revealed that only 35.55% of Polish students were engaged in high physical activity as opposed to 69.67% and 72.86% of school students in the present study. Most of the Polish students were classified as engaged in moderate physical activity (43.61%) compared to the 16.58% or 19% of the Slovakian students [15]. The obtained results were statistically non-significant ($0.7312; p < 0.05$).

Figure 1. Comparison of physical activity levels between grammar and vocational school students

Figure 2 shows that the body mass in 65.67% of grammar school students and 61.31% of vocational school students was considered normal for their age. According to Eurostat [16] only 45% of the adult European population are

considered to have normal body mass relative to their age. The vocational school students were more obese (+2.36%) and overweight (+9.12%) than the grammar schools students. The obesity numbers worldwide have

skyrocketed since 2000, and it is estimated that 13% of the world's population is currently obese [17]. Only 2.67% and 5.03% of students from both school types were obese. The results of the present study show that 17.67% of grammar school and 10.55% of vocational school students were underweight, which is a significant difference compared to 3% of the underweight adult population in the EU [18]. The students' body mass distribution results were statistically significant (0.0076; $p < 0.01$). Table 2 presents vigorous intensity physical activity levels of the Slovakian grammar and vocational school students. The median values indicate that the students from vocational schools engaged in physical activity of vigorous intensity 33% more than their grammar schools counterparts. In terms of time spent engaging in physical activity at that intensity, the vocational school students spent approximately 10.5 minutes a week of vigorous intensity activity

more than the grammar school students. The differences in minutes spent per week were statistically significant (0.0049; $p < 0.01$). In comparison, students from Turkey scored a median MET-minutes/week of 814, i.e. higher than the grammar school students, but lower than vocational school students in the present study. On the other hand, Polish students scored 2701, i.e. substantially higher than both groups of the Slovakian school students [15]. Table 3 includes the questionnaire answers regarding moderate-intensity physical activity. The vocational school students on average engaged in physical activity with moderate intensity for 12.5 minutes a week longer than the grammar school students. The median MET-minutes/week scores were also slightly higher (20%) in the group of vocational school students. The differences in time per minutes a week were statistically significant (0.0019; $p < 0.01$).

Figure 2. Body mass distribution in the groups of grammar and vocational schools students

Table 2. Levels of physical activity of vigorous intensity in MET-minutes/week, days per week, and minutes per week among grammar and vocational school students

Vigorous intensity physical activity	Grammar school students	Vocational school students	Statistical significance
Mean MET	1023.87	1107.73	0.4187
Median MET	720	960	
Min MET	0	0	
Max MET	7248	8400	
Time/min	45.41	55.9	0.0049*
Days/week	2.40	2.16	0.1166

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Table 3. Physical activity levels with moderate intensity in MET-minutes/week, days per week, and minutes per week

Moderate intensity physical activity	Grammar school students	Vocational school students	Statistical significance
Mean MET	659.33	787.76	0.5852
Median MET	480	600	
Min MET	0	0	
Max MET	4320	4200	
Time/min	52.05	64.55	0.0019*
Days/week	2.58	2.75	0.3034

Table 4 lists the students' answer scores regarding their walking-intensity physical activity. The amount of time spent walking by the students from both groups was almost identical, with the difference below one minute. In terms of the number of days, it can be concluded that walking was the most common physical activity among the respondents. Both grammar and vocational school students walked almost 5 days a week, which is comparable with 70% of Europeans aged 15-24, who walk 4 to 7 days a week [22]. Differences between the two surveyed groups of students were statistically non-significant ($p < 0.05$).

European adults spend approximately 300 minutes a day sitting, which is exactly the same for vocational school students in the present study [20]. Grammar schools students spend their time sitting an hour a day longer than the European median. This one-hour difference between grammar schools students and vocational schools students can be caused by the more demanding grammar school curriculum requiring more studying time. The difference in sitting time between the two groups of students was statistically significant ($1.75482E-06; p < 0.01$).

Table 4. Walking time of grammar and vocational schools students in MET-minutes/week, days per week, and minutes a day

Walking	Grammar school students	Vocational school students	Statistical significance
Mean MET	899.22	933.57	0.6650
Median MET	594	594	
Min MET	0	0	
Max MET	4851	4158	
Time/min	57.29	58.17	0.8318
Days/week	4.67	4.67	0.9918

Table 5. Time spent sitting in minutes per week by grammar and vocational school students

Time spent sitting	Grammar school students	Vocational school students	Total
Mean	378.09	311.46	344.78
Median	360	300	330

Discussion

The increasing sedentary lifestyle of both teenagers and adults has been widely observed. According to the American Heart Association, sedentary jobs have increased by 83 percent since the 1950s [1]. In order to assess whether the fourth wave of COVID-19 pandemic had an impact on the physical abilities of grammar and vocational school

students in eastern Slovakia we decided to conduct a study and asked students 7 simple questions using the International Physical Activity Questionnaire – Short Form (IPAQ-SF). The IPAQ is commonly regarded as one of the most widely used tools for evaluation of various types and levels of physical activity [21].

The mean sum of physical activity expressed in MET-minutes/week in the surveyed grammar school students (2.582) and vocational school students (2.829) from Slovakia was lower compared with students from Bosnia and Herzegovina (5.316) or from Poland (5.954), who engaged in physical activity twice as much as the Slovakian students [22, 23].

Physical inactivity and sedentary lifestyle entail health risks that must be addressed independently in order to investigate their harmful outcomes [24]. The ever expanding offer of sedentary jobs that do not require any physical activity has become a global concern. Genin et al. [25] consider sedentariness one of the main causes of preventable premature mortality. Many studies have already shown that physical activity can and does improve health. The World Health Organization recommends taking up at least 75 minutes of vigorous-intensity physical activity or 150 minutes of moderate intensity physical activity per week for all adults up to 64 years of age.

The present study examined the physical activity, its importance, health related risks and benefits, and various levels in grammar and vocational school students from eastern Slovakia. The study revealed the amount of time the students spent walking and sitting, and included recommendations from various authors on how much physical activity was needed to maintain a healthy lifestyle.

Conclusion

Physical activity and its benefits have been explained multiple times. This study conducted in eastern Slovakia revealed the

significant effect of the fourth wave of COVID-19 pandemic on the physical activity of grammar and vocational school students. The respondents' questionnaire answers were compared and analyzed statistically. Significant associations were found in body mass distribution, time spent engaging in moderate and vigorous physical activity, and sitting time, between the grammar and vocational school students. The limitations of this study include its regional focus, use of the short version of International Physical Activity Questionnaire, and the limited age groups of respondents. On the other hand, the application of IPAQ-SF can be beneficial as it has been a widely used questionnaire research worldwide. The results of this study suggest that the warning signals of many experts and scholars are slowly but surely becoming an everyday reality. The study findings support and even enhance those by other scholars, for example, revealing Slovakian grammar school students spending 6 hours a day sitting compared to 5 hours median of European adults [20]. Some findings may be quite surprising, for example, 18% of grammar school students reported to be underweight.

The study demonstrates an interesting correlation between body mass distribution and physical activity levels: 23% of vocational school students reported to be overweight compared with 14% of grammar school students, even though the former engaged in physical activity on each level more than the latter. Furthermore, the importance of movement, physical activity, and healthy lifestyle now more than ever before cannot be underestimated when taking into consideration all the factors and external threats common among not only some but all generations.

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